

ON SOME ISSUES OF PARLIAMENTARY CONTROL IN THE FINANCIAL AND BUDGETARY SPHERE

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Abstract: At present, the institution of parliamentary control is one of the elements of democracy and is an effective instrument by which society, represented by its representatives, gains the opportunity to control power, allows us to evaluate the effectiveness of its actions and is one of the main conditions for eradicating corruption and, accordingly, increasing public confidence in government institutions.

The article is aimed at analyzing general issues of parliamentary control in the budgetary and financial sphere, studying the practice of implementing parliamentary control in this area in some foreign countries.

Key words: Constitution, legislation, legal basis, legislative power, parliament, parliamentary control, parliamentary control, budgetary control, financial control, budget.

Control in the financial and budgetary spheres is one of the popular forms of parliamentary control. Control and compliance in this sphere are a kind of critical attributes, the most important qualities that all countries should strive to achieve. They mean that expenditures are within budget limits, that all expenditures comply with relevant laws and regulations, and that such expenditures are intended only for public policy and public interest purposes. The effectiveness of financial control presupposes not only the optimal use of state financial control methods, but also the rational use of budgetary funds and material assets[1]. Parliament, through the approval of the budget and, in most countries, the adoption of an accompanying budget law, should dominate the approach to oversight. The Ministry of Finance is responsible for overall operational control of the budget, reporting to Parliament and, if changes to budget expenditure are necessary, seeking Parliament's approval. Noel Hepworth argues that the Budget Act should focus on financial constraints rather than the "outcomes" to be achieved, although statements accompanying the Budget are likely to include broad policy objectives rather than specific

management targets. Some countries have experimented with different forms of budgeting, such as program budgeting and performance budgeting, to increase the focus on 'results', but with varying degrees of success. Such budget reforms are usually not accompanied in developing and transition countries by any of the governance reforms that are necessary for them to be effective[2]. In the UK, control over finance is control over funds already approved by Parliament. The House of Commons' scrutiny of government spending consists of scrutiny of the estimates of expenditure submitted to the House by departments when approving the Appropriation Act, and scrutiny of the expenditure reports by the Public Accounts Committee. The parliamentary scrutiny of the accounts is based on the report of a special officer of the House of Commons, the Comptroller and Auditor General, who exercises his powers on its behalf. Since 1983, this officer has been appointed by the government on the basis of a resolution of the House of Commons proposed by the Prime Minister with the approval of the chairman of the Public Accounts Committee of Parliament[3]. In the United States, the largest financial control agency, the General Accounting Office, created in 1921, reports to legislators. This office has access to virtually all financial documents of ministries and departments. On behalf of the chambers and the commission of Congress or its individual members, it can evaluate the effectiveness of state programs and the activities of federal departments; conduct special surveys and checks of the validity of prices for products, financial and economic aspects of contracts of the Ministry of Defense[1]. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the consideration and implementation of control over the execution of the State Budget is regulated in Article 7 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Parliamentary Control", according to which the Legislative Chamber exercises control over the execution of the State Budget. The Ministry of Economy and Finance of the Republic of Uzbekistan quarterly sends information and necessary materials on the progress of the State Budget execution to the Legislative Chamber. The Legislative Chamber reviews the progress of the State Budget execution for each quarter. During its consideration, the report of the Cabinet of Ministers,

the opinions and proposals of the factions, the corresponding conclusion of the responsible committee of the Legislative Chamber are heard, a discussion is held and a corresponding resolution is adopted. The Cabinet of Ministers, no later than 15 May of the year following the reporting year, shall submit to the Legislative Chamber an annual report on the execution of the State Budget, together with the conclusion of the Accounts Chamber. The Legislative Chamber examines the annual report on the execution of the State Budget submitted by the Cabinet of Ministers on the basis of its preliminary discussion in factions and committees of the Legislative Chamber. During the preliminary discussion of the issue of the progress of the execution of the State Budget, factions and committees of the Legislative Chamber may request additional information from the relevant bodies regarding the execution of the revenue portion of the State Budget, the status of the development of allocated funds, as well as information on their targeted spending and effective use. At the same time, factions can initiate a study by the committees of the Legislative Chamber at the local level of issues of targeted spending and effective use of budget funds. After discussion in factions and committees of the Legislative Chamber, the annual report on the execution of the State Budget is considered at a meeting of the Legislative Chamber and approved by a resolution of the Legislative Chamber. Accordingly, it can be noted that in world practice, responsibility for the effectiveness of budget execution most often lies with the Ministry of Finance or other financial bodies, which, within any framework established by parliament, will dominate the control process, requiring public organizations to comply with its requirements. In other words, it is the Ministry of Finance and other financial bodies that will ensure and determine the application of control processes and how these control processes will operate. Based on this, the aim will be to ensure that, through control mechanisms, expenditures comply with budgetary limits, i.e. the “costs” specified in the Budget Act[4]. Thus, parliamentary control in the financial and budgetary sphere is, first of all, the authority of parliaments to approve the list of state income and expenditure, as well as to establish taxes. Although

this power is usually exercised in the form of a law, it represents a special part of parliamentary competence, as is also evidenced by the fact that the relevant laws are often adopted according to a special procedure that differs from the procedure for adopting ordinary laws.

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